

**WORK RELATED STRESS AND SOCIAL SKILLS AMONG LOCAL
GOVERNMENT PERSONNEL**

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ABSTRACT

Work-related stress is a serious problem and the inability to balance work and life may increase stress. The study was conducted to determine which domain of work-related stress best predict the social skills among government employees. The researcher used a descriptive correlation method. There are 100 government employees as the respondents in the survey. Adopted questionnaires were used in the collection of data among government employees. Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression were used for data analysis. Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the level of work-related stress among government employees is high. Conversely, their level of social skills is very high. In addition, work-related stress is related to social skills and work overload as an indicator of work-related stress can best predict social skills among government employees. The company should have a team activity or team building to boost employee's self-esteem, morale, and help personnel's get to know each other in a non-stressful capacity is by offering an occasional company outing for socialization. Moreover, encourage the employee to attend training, workshops to enhance their skills, and communication well effectively. The fast paced communication of social media and new technologies can impact everyone's knowledge-based will help employee's master new technology.

KEYWORDS:

Work-Related Stress, Social Skills, Local Government, Personnel

INTRODUCTION

The inability to manage work and life may lead to increase the rate of stress, according to Mann & Holdsworth (2003), reducing the quality of Filipino workers' output and making them more prone to hypertension and heart disease. Work-related stress adversely affects employers and employees alike. According to the Department of Health-National Capital Region Director Eduardo Janairo, stress physically wears out the body. It puts people at risk to a lot of illnesses, from the common cold to hypertension and severe heart disease.

On a similar note, employees who are healthy, well organized, and relaxed are highly needed in any job. Healthy employees can perform well at their highest levels, have decreased absenteeism, and have fewer health claims than their unhealthy counterparts. Stress has a big impact on a workplace productivity including self-care issues such as diet and exercise and organizational issues like time management (Anderson & Bolt, 2013).

On the other hand, professional media practitioner to succeed, according to Amorim, Bursery, Janowiak, Mccarty, & Demeter (2018), an individual must possess social and interpersonal skills. Both social and interpersonal skills refer to the same thing and that is interaction with others. Strong interpersonal skills will be an advantage to talk and work with all types of people, including managers, co-workers, customers, and respondents. Having appropriate social skills allows a professional and most especially media practitioners to communicate and interact appropriately with other people. This is associated with both verbal and nonverbal communication through gestures, body language, and physical appearance (Mandal, 2014).

However, Jenkins (2009) stated that media relation is a large component of the public relations discipline and interpersonal skills play a vital role in building, fostering and maintaining a beneficial relationship with the media. The result contributes to the overall success of the public relations plan and embodies the basic definition of the public relations as described by the Public Relations Society of America: "Strategic communication process is a public relations that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organizations and their publics."

Moreover, work-related stress is a serious problem nowadays that needs to be addressed especially in a fast-paced environment. It is very important that this issue should be addressed and an action is taken to determine the problems that this may create both for individuals and the organizations in which individuals work. When pursuing a career or entering the workforce, you can expect to deal with all sorts of stress and it comes from all

sides. You might face pressure from your boss, co-workers, the corporation or business itself, and much more (Cohen, 2018).

OJECTIVE

The study was conducted to determine which domain of work-related stress best predict the social skills among government employees.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a descriptive correlation method. This method is appropriate in determining the relationship between work-related stress and social skills among government employees. There are 100 government employees as the respondents in the survey. Questionnaires were adopted and given to the respondents by the researcher. Adopted questionnaires for work-related stress and social skills were used in the collection of data among government employees. This was personally administered to the respondents by the researcher. The survey conducted is in compliant to the research survey ethics protocol which reserved the confidentiality of the personal information of the participants. The collected data were collated and tallied for statistical analysis. Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression were used for data analysis. In accepting and rejecting the null hypothesis, alpha is set at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Level of Work-Related Stress of Government Employees*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Work Overload	0.60	3.92	High
Time Deadline	0.64	3.88	High
Overall	0.52	3.90	High

Table 1 presents a summary of all the indicators of work-related stress among government employees. The overall items gathered a mean value of 3.90 or high. This means that government employees often deal with work overload and time deadline. Additionally, they happened to accept challenges and perform thoroughly at work and make sure to meet the deadline. Furthermore, they tend to cope with different stress through various kinds of activities (Lazarus & Folkman, 1987).

Table 2. *Level of Social Skills of Government Employees*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Cooperation	0.52	4.30	Very High
Responsibility	0.40	4.36	Very High
Overall	0.42	4.34	Very High

Table 2 unfolds the summary of all indicators of social skills stresses among government employees. The overall items gathered a mean value of 4.34 or very high. This means that government employees always deal with cooperation and responsibility. Additionally, they always make sure to pursue camaraderie through joining in team buildings and getting along well with colleagues without comprising the responsibility that their job requires (Stanley & Algert, 2007).

Table 3. *Significant Relationship between Work-Related Stress and Social Skills among Government Employees*

Work Related Stress	Social Skills		
	Cooperation	Responsibility	Overall
Work Overload	.292** (.041)	.015 (.211)	.211** .032
Time Deadline	.227** (.013)	.141 (.718)	.214** (.001)
Overall	.221** (.011)	.021 (.552)	.251** (.002)

Table 3 shows the correlation of the variables between work-related stress and social skills among government employees. It can be observed that work-related stress is related to social skills with the overall r-value of .251** with the P value of .002 which is greater than .05 level of significance. The result is significant and thus the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that social skills are dependent on their work-related stress. Furthermore, work-related stress has to do with social skills among government employees. This further implies that the higher is the work-related stress the higher is their social skills (Schaufeli, Bakker & Van Rhenen, 2009).

Table 4. *Domain of Work-Related Stress Best Predict Social Skills of Government Employees*

Work Related Stress	Social Skills			
	Unstandardized Beta	Standardized Beta	t-value	Sig.
Work Overload	.365	.542	5.322	.000
Time Deadline	.285	.425	5.427	.000
R	.822			
R square	.672			
F-value	64.02			
P-value	.000			

Table 4 presents the domain of the work-related stress that best predicts the social skills of the media practitioners. Work overload is the domain of work related stress that best predict social skills of government employees as revealed in the t-value of 5.322 with the p-value of .000 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. The result is significant and rejection of the null hypothesis. Work overload as an indicator can singly predict the social skills of government employees.

However, when the domains of work-related stress are combined, they garnered an R-value of .822 with the R-square of .672 equivalent to 67.2%. The variance of 32.8% is attributed to other variables not covered in this study. The overall F-value of 64.02 with the p-value of .000, means that work-related stress has a significant influence on the social skills of government employees and it is congruent to the study of Jerkins (2009).

Table 5. *Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Work Overload*

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
WORK OVERLOAD			
1. I will accept it as a challenge and eventually will take a rest after work is done	0.86	4.43	Very High
2. I will learn to deal with the changes	0.67	4.16	High
3. I will start to find an alternative job	0.78	4.25	Very High
4. I will look over to my resources	1.18	3.57	High
5. I will cope with stress through leisure activities	0.92	4.10	High
Overall	0.62	4.12	High

Table 5 displays the level of work-related stress of media practitioners in terms of work overload with the mean rating of 4.12 which is high. This means that they accept it as a challenge and eventually takes a short rest after work is done. They cope up with stress through leisure activities, Maslach & Leiter (2008) stated that they learn to deal with the changes, so they start to find an alternative job and they look over their resources.

Table 6. *Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Time Deadline*

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
TIME DEADLINE			
1. I do physical exercises	1.23	3.53	High
2. I pray, meditate and embrace the reality	1.23	3.53	High
3. I take a nap to divert thoughts	1.23	3.53	High
4. I make a to-do list	1.23	3.53	High
5. I pamper myself through spa and other form of relaxation.	1.23	3.53	High
Overall	0.65	3.85	High

Table 6 is the level of work-related stress of media practitioners in terms of the deadline with the mean rating of 3.85 or high. This means that they do physical exercises, meditating and embracing the reality, taking a nap to divert thoughts, making a to-do list and pampering themselves through spa and other form of relaxation.

Moreover, they claim that they often do physical exercises, praying, meditating and embracing the reality, taking a nap to divert thoughts, making a to-do list and pampering themselves through spa and other form of relaxation with the same mean rating of 3.53 of high on each line item (Silver, 2012).

Table 7. *Level of Social Skills in Terms of Cooperation*

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
COOPERATION			
1. Join team activity or team building and participate on activities provided by the company	0.85	4.29	Very High
2. Follow supervisor's direction	0.85	4.29	Very High
3. Use words like "please" when asking for favors	0.85	4.29	Very High
4. Start conversation with colleagues and newbie in the studio or office	0.85	4.29	Very High
5. Talk things over with co-workers when there's a problem or arguments	0.85	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.59	4.38	High

Table 7 indicates the level of social skills of media practitioners in terms of cooperation with the mean rating of 4.38 or very high. This mean that they join team activity or team building and participate on activities provided by the company, follow the supervisor's directions, use words like "please" when asking for a favour, start conversation with colleagues and newly hired in the studio or office and talk things over with co-workers when there's problem or arguments.

Moreover, they claim that they always join team activity or team building and participate on activities provided by the company, follow the supervisor's directions, use words like "please" when asking for favours, start conversation with colleagues and newbies in the studio or office and talk things over with co-workers when there's a problem or arguments with the same mean rating of 4.29 or very high (Gursoy & Karadag, 2013).

Table 8. *Level of Social Skills in Terms of Responsibility*

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
RESPONSIBILITY			
1. I listen to my supervisor and colleagues during the meetings and share my ideas to them	0.53	4.67	Very High
2. Do my assigned work	0.53	4.67	Very High
3. Keep my desk clean	0.53	4.67	Very High
4. Submit reports on time	0.53	4.67	Very High
5. Finish assigned work on time	0.53	4.67	Very High
Overall	0.44	4.46	Very High

Table 8 shows the level of social skills of media practitioners in terms of responsibility with the mean rating of 4.46 or very high. This means that they listen to their supervisor and colleagues during meetings and share their ideas to them, do their assigned work, keep their desk clean, submit reports on time and finish assigned work on time.

Moreover, they claim that they always listen to their supervisor and colleagues during meetings and share their ideas to them, do their assigned work, keep their desk clean, submit reports in time and finished the

assigned work on time with the same mean rating of 4.6 or very high on each line item (Alfonso & Suzanne, 2008).

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the level of work-related stress among government employees is high. Conversely, their level of social skills is very high. Moreover, work-related stress is related to social skills and work overload as an indicator of work-related stress can best predict social skills among government employees.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were formulated based on the findings of the study: The company should have a team activity or team building to boost employee's self-esteem, morale, and help personnel's get to know each other in a non-stressful capacity is by offering an occasional company outing for socialization. Moreover, encourage the employee to attend training, workshops to enhance their skills, and communication well effectively. The fast paced communication of social media and new technologies can impact everyone's knowledge-based will help employee's master new technology.

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